

Clinico-Histopathological Profile of Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic Pigmentary Skin Lesions in a Tertiary Care Centre of West Uttar-PradeshNeha Pathania¹, Mithila Bisht², Nitesh Mohan³, Sheetal Mishra⁴¹Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly²Professor, Department of Pathology, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly³Professor, Department of Pathology, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Skin, the largest organ of the human body, is extraordinarily vibrant regarding diversity and complexity of function it serves. Long term exposure to harmful UV rays and pollutants and the environment helps in the development of pigmented lesions on the skin. Diagnosis of skin disease requires clinical details such as site, distribution, color and regional arrangements in most of the clinical findings but making diagnosis solely on clinical symptoms is quite challenging and must be supplemented with biopsy and histopathology almost always.

Materials and Methods: This is a hospital based retrospective study carried out for seven months in Department of Pathology RMCH, where clinical histopathological evaluation of 80 cases of dermatological pigmentary lesions with subsequent available biopsies was studied.

Results: Among 80 cases of pigmentary skin lesions analyzed, 71 were non-neoplastic and only 9 cases were of neoplastic origin. These cases were further categorized, into hyper-pigmented (53 cases, 66.3%), hypo-pigmented (19 cases, 23.7%) and both hyper/hypo-pigmented (8 cases, 10%) skin lesion. The lesion comprised of 33 infectious skin lesions, 14 cases of immune mediated skin lesions, 24 cases of inflammatory skin lesions, 4 benign neoplastic skin lesions and 5 cases of malignant neoplastic skin lesions. The age range was from 1 to 75 years with slight male predominance (58.8%) and limbs being the most common site involved. Clinicohistopathological correlation showed positive correlation in 54 cases (67.5%), negative correlation in 13 cases (16.2%) and inconclusive in 13 cases (16.2%).

Conclusion: The incidence of skin lesions in the study population was higher than assumed, with prevalence of non-neoplastic and neoplastic skin disease increasing with age. In cases where skin biopsy delivered a non-specific diagnosis, neoplastic etiology was ruled out. Histopathological studies are needed to help assess the pattern of skin disease based on pathological evaluation to develop public health strategies and to have clinicopathological correlation.

Keywords: Pigmentary, Skin Lesions, Clinicopathologic Correlation, Neoplastic.

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Introduction

Pigmentary skin lesions are one of the most frequent causes for dermatologic consultations. These lesions are a heterogeneous set of illnesses linked to changes in skin's pigmentation patterns and intensity. These can be inherited or acquired because of changes in melanin synthesis, defects in melanosome transfer to keratinocytes, and aberrant melanocyte migration from the neural crest to the skin during embryogenesis. [1] The fact that nevi and other benign pigmented lesions are a major risk factor for malignant melanoma, pigmentation defects might represent underlying pathology in addition to being cosmetic deformities that disturb people psychologically. [2] There are pigmented

variations of several non-melanocytic skin lesions that might be difficult to diagnose and mistaken for clinically melanocytic lesions. Histopathological analysis aids in the management of patients with pigmentary skin lesions as well as the confirmation or refutation of the clinical diagnosis. We hope to assess the range of these lesions in this study and establish a correlation between the histological and clinical diagnosis. [3]

Materials and Methods

A tertiary care hospital based retrospective study spanning over a period of seven months was done in Department of Pathology, RMCH. A total of 80

patients of all age groups having pigmentary skin lesions clinically were included in the study. These lesions were analyzed considering the histological type and anatomical location, tumor type along with the age and gender.

Patients who failed to give their consent were excluded from the study. For histopathological examination, Hematoxylin and Eosin stain formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissue sections were examined. Special stains were performed whenever necessary. All these slides were evaluated by 2 independent consultant pathologists. In case of discrepancy opinion of 3rd consultant was sought.

Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee, RMCH. The collected data was entered in the Microsoft Office excel software. Data analysis was done by using SPSS (Statistical

Package for Social Science) 23.0 version. The study considered 95% confidence interval.

Inclusion Criteria: The study covered both neoplastic and non-neoplastic pigmented skin lesions from all age groups and both genders.

Exclusion Criteria: In adequate biopsy specimens and skin biopsies other than pigmented lesions were eliminated from the research. Also, patients who fail to give their consent were excluded from this study.

Results

Histopathological study of 80 cases of pigmentary skin lesions were evaluated where maximum cases encountered were non-neoplastic (71 cases, 88.8%) (fig.1) with slight male predominance (47 cases, 58.8%) (fig.2)

Figure 1: Types of skin lesions

Figure 2: Gender distribution

These cases were further categorized, into hyper-pigmented (53 cases, 66.3%), hypo-pigmented (19 cases, 23.7%) and both hyper/hypo-pigmented (8 cases, 10%) skin lesions (fig.3).

Figure 3: Pigmentary skin lesions

In the study population, the age range was from birth to 75 years and most cases were in the age group of 16-30 years (n=38 cases, 47.5%) followed by 31-45 years (n=22 cases, 27.5%). Least cases were seen at extreme of age i.e. age of 61-75 years (n=2 cases, 2.5%) and birth to 15 years (n=5 cases, 6.25%) (fig.4).

Figure 4: Age distribution

Most common site involved was limbs (n=31 cases, 38.8%) followed by head and neck region (n=17 cases, 21.3%) in all pigmentary skin lesions (table 1, fig.5)

Table 1: Anatomic distribution of pigmentary skin lesions

Correlation	Non-Neoplastic	Neoplastic
Head & Neck (17 cases, 21.3%)	13	04
Thorax (09 cases, 11.3%)	09	00
Abdomen (03 cases, 3.7%)	03	00
Limbs (31 cases, 38.8%)	28	03
Back (08 cases, 10%)	07	01
All over body (12 cases, 15%)	11	01

Figure 5: Anatomic distribution of pigmentary skin lesions

In this study an analysis of the clinical diagnosis with the histopathological diagnosis revealed a positive correlation in total 54 cases (67.5%) and negative correlation in 13 cases (16.2%) with 13 cases (16.2%) as inconclusive of definitive diagnosis (Table.2, Fig.6).

Table 2: Clinico-Histopathological diagnostic correlation

Correlation	Non-Neoplastic	Neoplastic
Agreement	49	05
Disagreement	09	04
Inconclusive	13	00

Figure 6: Clinico-Histopathological diagnostic correlation

Discussion

In our study of pigmented skin lesions, majority of lesions were hyper-pigmented 53 cases (66.3%) which was concordant with the study done by Bohra et.al. [4], Parvathi et. al. [5], Leishram et. al. [6], where 60-70% of cases were hyper-pigmented but was discordant when compared with study by Prasad et al. [7] where hypo-pigmented lesions

were slightly predominant. Maximum cases seen were of Leprosy (n=20 cases, 25%) followed by Chronic Non Specific Dermatoses (n=8 cases, 10%). Pyoderma gangrenosum (n=1), Pilomatricoma (n=1) were the skin lesions which were seen least (Table.3).

Our study was male predominant 58.8% with male: female ratio 1.4:1, which was similar to the study

by Suvernakar et. al. [2] where male: female ratio was 1.1:1. The sex distribution in our study was also similar to study by Crasta J et al. [3] (male:female= 1.2:1) and by Youl PH et. al. [8] (male: female = 1.4:1).

Majority of skin lesions were seen below 50 years of age which was concordant to Leishram et. al. [6], Parvathi et. al. [5], Schafer et. al. [9], Mackie et al. [10], where majority of patients were above 40 years of age. Our age distribution findings were dissimilar with Youl et. al.[8].

Most frequent involved site was limbs 38.8% which was discordant with the study done by Bohra et.al. [4], where the most common site was head and neck (58.7%) followed by lower limbs (15.2%) and upper limbs (2.2%). Similar pattern was seen in study by Parvathi et. al. [5], Leishram et. al. [6], where most common site was head and neck region which was discordant with our findings. In study done by Kumar S et al. [11], malignant pigmentary

skin lesions were seen on head and neck region in 97.2% of cases which is similar to findings of our study where most common region involved by malignant pigmentary skin lesions was head and neck region in 44.4% of cases.

Clinical and histological concordance was achieved in 54 cases (67.5%) which is comparable to Parvathi et. al. [5] observation where 66% of clinical diagnosis showed positive correlation with histopathological diagnosis.

Increased concern among public and health care professionals regarding the malignant skin lesions had led to increase in number of biopsies being done over the time. The overall diagnostic accuracy of clinically evaluated pigmented skin lesions is 67.5% which is slightly higher than in study by Curley RK et al. [12], where overall sensitivity was 50%. This increased diagnostic accuracy points towards the utility and importance of histopathology in arriving at conclusive diagnosis.

Table 3: Diagnosed pigmentary skin lesions

Lesions		Number of Cases (80)
Non- Neoplastic (N = 71 cases)	Leprosy	20
	Lupus Vulgaris	4
	Chromoblastomycosis	2
	Verruca Vulgaris	7
	Lupus Erythematosus	5
	Vesicobullous lesions	2
	Leucocytoclastic Vasculitis	2
	Amyloidosis	2
	Scleroderma	3
	Lichen Planus	6
	Chronic nonspecific dermatoses	8
	Pityriasis	5
	Psoriasis	2
	Calcinosis Cutis	2
	Pyoderma gangrenosum	1
Benign Neoplastic (N= 04 cases)	Intradermal Naevus	1
	Congenital melanocytic naevus	1
	Epidermal naevus	1
	Pilomatricoma	1
Malignant Neoplastic (N=05 cases)	Basal cell carcinoma	3
	Verrucous squamous cell carcinoma	1
	Malignant melanoma	1

Most common skin lesion encountered was Leprosy (n=20 cases), which is chronic cutaneous infection caused by Mycobacterium leprae. Also called Hansen Disease is clinically characterized progressive hypo-pigmented and erythematous skin lesions (fig.7). Microscopically in different types of

leprosy we can see leprosy bacilli, epithelioid histiocytes, langhans giant cell, thinned out epidermis, grenz zone, etc (fig.8). Most common diagnosis in leprosy was given as indeterminate leprosy; followed by lepromatous leprosy and least diagnosed was tuberculoid leprosy.

Figure 7: Hypo-pigmented and raised skin lesions in leprosy

Figure 8: Grenz zone and thinned out normal epidermis on microscopy in leprosy

Second most common lesion found was chronic non-specific dermatoses (n=8) which is a group of chronic and relapsing skin conditions that cause inflamed skin, signs and symptoms of atopic dermatitis include rash, pruritus and xerosis. 7 cases of Verrucae Vulgaris (common wart) caused

by HPV were diagnosed. Clinically it showed hyperkeratotic papules with pinpoint black dots (thrombosed capillaries)(fig.9). Microscopically hyperkeratosis, papillomatosis, hypergranulosis, rete ridges lengthening and thickening was observed (fig.10)

Figure 9: Hyperkeratotic papule without pinpoint black dots (Verrucae Vulgaris)

Figure 10: Lengthening and thickening of rete ridges seen in Verrucae Vulgaris (common wart) on microscopy

4 cases of Lupus Vulgaris were diagnosed which is most common form of re-infection tuberculosis. Clinically ulcerated lesions, developing into disfiguring skin ulcers (tuberculoid chancre) were noted (fig.11). Histologically, early lesions had mixed dense inflammatory infiltrates, necrosis and ulceration. Later on, granulomas, giant cells, acanthosis, hypergranulosis, hyperkeratosis and follicular plunging was also seen (fig.12).

Figure 11: Disfigured skin ulcer in Lupus Vulgaris

Figure 12: Hyperkeratosis with follicular plugging, with mixed inflammatory infiltrates and ulceration on microscopy of Lupus Vulgaris

2 cases of chronic deep cutaneous fungal infection known as Chromoblastomycosis was noted with characteristic small firm red, gray bump on traumatized skin. Histology showed mononuclear cell infiltrate and a dark-brown, round sclerotic body resembling a “copper penny”(fig.13).

Figure 13: Brown, round sclerotic body (copper-penny body) on microscopy of Chromoblastomycosis

5 cases of cutaneous lupus erythematosus were diagnosed which showed raised pink-red lesions with central clearing clinically (fig.14,15). Microscopically, it showed vacuolar interface changes, apoptosis keratinocytes and perivascular lymphocytic infiltration, dyskeratotic keratinocytes extending into upper spinous layer.

Figure 14: Raised reddish skin lesions with central clearing in case of Cutaneous Lupus Erythematosus

Figure 15: Erythematous skin lesion on face in case of Cutaneous Lupus Erythematosus

2 cases of vesicobullous lesion, were diagnosed clinically there was fluid filled bullae noted (fig.16). Microscopically, fluid filled cavities within or beneath the epidermis were noted which were filled with inflammatory infiltrates predominantly eosinophils (fig.17).

Figure 16: Fluid filled bullae seen in Vesicobullous lesions

Figure 17: Cavity formed beneath epidermis filled with inflammatory infiltrates in Vesicobullous lesions

6 patients presented with purple, pruritic, planar (flat), polygonal papules and plaques were clinically diagnosed with classical lichen planus (fig.18). Histologically, saw toothed rete ridges, band like lymphohistiocytic infiltrate at the dermoepidermal junction and wedge shaped hypergranulosis was noted and diagnosis of lichen planus was found consistent with findings (fig.19).

Figure 18: Raised, reddish-purple papules and plaques seen in Lichen planus

Figure 19: On microscopy saw toothed rete ridges, hypergranulosis and infiltrates at dermo-epidermal junction (Classic Lichen planus)

2 patients presented with well demarcated erythematous papules and plaques with silvery white scales (fig.20). On microscopy, loss of granular layer and supra-papillary thinning, hyperkeratosis and parakeratosis was noted and these cases were diagnosed as Psoriasis (fig.21).

Figure 20: Demarcated erythematous lesions with silvery white scales seen in Psoriasis

Figure 21: Supra-papillary thinning with loss of granular layer in Psoriasis

5 cases of self-limited viral exanthema was seen in young patients, microscopically patchy parakeratosis, reduced granular cell layer, mild acanthosis and mild spongiosis was observed. These cases were diagnosed as Pityriasis rosea. In benign neoplastic skin lesions Naevus was most common (n=3 cases), which can be congenital or acquired benign melanocytic tumor. Clinically,

patient had hyper-pigmented skin lesion which was dark brown to black in color (fig.22).

Microscopically, nests of melanocytes were noted which were uniform in size and distributed predominantly over the edges of rete ridges (fig.10.c).

Figure 22: Black or Dark brown skin lesions in cases of Naevus

Figure 23: Melanocytes of uniform size at edge of rete ridges (Naevus)

Amongst malignant skin lesions, Basal cell carcinoma is the most common entity (n=3 cases, fig.24). It arises from interfollicular or follicular epithelium, showing nests of basaloid cells with peripheral palisading associated with fibromyxoid stroma (fig.25).

Figure 24: Hypo/hyper-pigmented raised skin lesions (malignant)

Figure 25: Nests of basaloid cells arranged in palisading pattern (Basal Cell Carcinoma)

All histopathological diagnosis was correlated clinically and definitive histopathological diagnosis was possible in 67 cases. In the rest 13 cases, no histopathological diagnosis could be made as 5 cases biopsy was inadequate to comment upon, while in 8 cases no specific pattern of disease was observed. It emphasizes the importance of performing the skin biopsy at appropriate phase of disease, from proper site, of proper thickness to reach at a relevant diagnosis.

Conclusion

Pigmentary skin lesions are a relatively common presenting condition, most of them are benign, but a tiny percentage may be cancerous. Clinically significant pigmentary skin lesions histopathological analysis, distinguishes malignant tumors from benign lesions.

Histopathological study of pigmentary skin lesions is important because early detection and treatment, of lesions are critical to reduce functional and cosmetic morbidity and expenses.

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